

Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric Acid Complexes with Transition Metals

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Manuscript received 14 May 1976, revised 20 September 1977, accepted 7 July 1978

The complexes of transition metal ions with di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid have been investigated by the potentiometric technique in 75% aqueous dioxan media in the presence of 0.1M sodium perchlorate. The proton-ligand stability constants and the stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-titration technique modified by Irving and Rossotti. The log K values have been computed by the weighted least Square's method. The values of stepwise and overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° accompanying the complex formation reactions have been evaluated by carrying out the experiments at 30°, 40°, 45° and 50°. It is found that as the temperature increases the stability of complexes decreases.

THE equilibria study of the metal complexes of tolyl derivatives of thiovioluric acid, and their thermodynamics have received comparatively little attention. Some physical constants have been reported in the literature^{1,2}. In this paper stability constants and acid dissociation constants at different temperatures have been evaluated; changes in thermodynamic parameters for different complexes is being reported.

Experimental

Materials: Di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid was prepared by the general method outlined by Dutt and coworkers³.

Stock solution of the ligand was prepared in freshly distilled dioxan. All the metal ion solutions were prepared from A.R. B.D.H. samples of corresponding nitrates or sulphates and were standardised by conventional gravimetric procedures.

Chemically pure sodium perchlorate (Riedal) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. A 0.05 M solution of tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) in 75% dioxan (aqueous) was used as the titrant.

Dioxan used was purified by refluxing on sodium wire for 24 hr and was freshly distilled over sodium before use.

Apparatus: A Beckmann pH-meter, expandomatic, SS-2 model, in conjunction with a glass and calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. The pH-meter was standardised with aqueous buffers, and in the calculation of free ligand concentration the pH-meter readings were directly used. The use of the pH-meter readings instead of true pH values do not involve any error, in the calculation of free ligand concentration^{4,5}.

Pre-saturated nitrogen (with 75% aqueous dioxan) was passed through the solutions during the titrations. The temperature was maintained using a thermostat having an accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$

Proton-ligand and Metal-ligand Stability Constants

In order to calculate these constants, the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti was employed⁶. The following solutions (total volume=19.67 ml due to contraction on mixing dioxan and water) were titrated potentiometrically against standard 0.05 M TMAH solution to find \bar{n} and pL values of the complexes.

- (i) 0.8 ml of HClO_4 (0.02M) + 1.0 ml of NaClO_4 (2M) + 2.7 ml of H_2O + 0.5 ml of Na_2SO_4 (0.02M) + 15.0 ml of dioxan.
- (ii) 0.8 ml of HClO_4 (0.02M) + 1.0 ml of NaClO_4 (2M) + 2.7 ml of H_2O + 0.5 ml of Na_2SO_4 (0.02M) + 10.0 ml of ligand (0.01M) + 5.0 ml of dioxan.
- (iii) 0.8 ml of HClO_4 (0.02M) + 1.0 ml of NaClO_4 (2M) + 2.7 ml of H_2O + 0.5 ml of metal nitrate or sulphate (0.02M) + 10.0 ml of ligand (0.01M) + 5.0 ml of dioxan.

From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii) the values of $pK(\text{OH})$ were calculated by plotting $\log \alpha/1-\alpha$ vs pH (where α is the degree of dissociation), when straight line having intercept equal to pK and slope equal to unity were obtained.

From the titration curves of solutions (i), (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} values of the metal complexes were determined at various pH values. From a knowledge of $pK(\text{OH})$ and those of \bar{n} values at different pH, the corresponding values of pL have been calculated.

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TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH DI-*p*-TOLYLTHIOVIOLURIC ACID AND $pK(OH)$ VALUES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AT $\mu=0.100M NaClO_4$

Temperature Cations	30°			40°			45°			50°		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₃
H ⁺	5.38			5.14			4.98			4.84		
Mn ²⁺	2.91	2.17	5.08	2.90	2.18	5.08	2.83	2.16	4.99	2.93	1.83	4.76
Cd ²⁺	3.09	2.78	5.87	3.15	2.64	5.99	3.23	2.32	5.61	3.28	2.18	5.47
Zn ²⁺	4.60	3.59	8.19	4.16	3.51	7.68	4.04	3.47	7.51	3.96	3.43	7.40
Pb ²⁺	3.79	4.61	8.41	4.24	3.54	7.79	4.09	3.56	7.66	4.02	3.34	7.37
Co ²⁺	4.58	4.08	8.67	4.27	3.78	8.06	4.18	3.69	7.88	4.12	3.56	7.68
Ni ²⁺	5.13	4.08	9.21	4.54	3.93	8.48	4.43	3.88	8.32	4.38	3.80	8.19
Fe ²⁺	4.81	3.94	8.76	4.58	3.96	8.54	4.47	3.91	8.38	4.40	3.75	8.15
Cu ²⁺	5.15	4.28	9.33	4.68	4.07	8.76	4.57	4.03	8.61	4.51	3.95	8.46
UO ₂ ²⁺	5.09	4.37	9.47	4.87	4.31	9.18	4.79	4.24	9.04	4.70	4.09	8.79

* Values obtained from weighted least squares method.

The formation curves have been plotted from the \bar{n} and pL values.

The stability constants were computed on an IBM 360 FORTRAN IV computer using a weighted least squares program patterned after that of Sullivan et al⁷. The β_n values were initially approximated from the data (\bar{n} , pL) with weight factor being unity. Using these approximate β_n 's weight factors were calculated. Then an improved set of β_n 's were obtained and the iterative procedure was repeated till successive cycles gave a change of less than one part, at the fifth decimal place, in each β_n .

The weighted least squares treatment determines that set of β_n 's which make the function U , $[U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y-x-nz)\beta_n x^n]$ nearest to zero, by minimizing

$$S(S = \sum_{i=1}^t w_i u^2(x_i, y_i, z_i)) \quad w, r, t \text{ variation parameters } \beta_n.$$

We are reporting the S_{min} values for respective metal complexes. S_{min} has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with k degrees of freedom, and with weight define in accordance with Sullivan et al⁸ we can put $S_{min} = \chi^2$ (Table 2).

\bar{n} values greater than 2.0 have not been obtained in any of the cases. It is therefore concluded that not more than two complexes, i.e., 1:1 and 1:2 (M:L) are formed in each system.

TABLE 2—SULLIVAN ET AL $S_{min}(S_{min} = \chi^2)$ VALUES FOR METAL COMPLEXES WITH DI-*p*-TOLYL THIOVIOLURIC ACID AT $\mu=0.1 M NaClO_4$

Temperature	30°	40°	45°	50°
	S_{min}	S_{min}	S_{min}	S_{min}
Mn ²⁺	0.00728	0.017879	0.0070263	0.005463
Cd ²⁺	0.07132	0.058226	0.0034019	0.011961
Zn ²⁺	0.13239	0.069357	0.055782	0.056802
Pb ²⁺	0.07047	0.093613	0.019898	0.094317
Co ²⁺	1.74620	0.104080	1.1275	0.055155
Ni ²⁺	1.24040	0.075396	0.067980	0.048927
Fe ²⁺	1.22820	0.064697	0.067980	0.053318
Cu ²⁺	1.55580	0.074135	0.062693	0.063642
UO ₂ ²⁺	3.54960	0.063286	0.078683	0.100920

In view of high metal to ligand ratio (1:10) used in the titrations, it has been assumed that the possibility of polynuclear complexes is negligible.

Results and Discussion

A review of values of stability constants in Table 1 reveals that as the temperature increases, the stability constant value decreases. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated by using the following relations⁹:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$d \log K/d(1/T) = \Delta H^\circ/4.57 \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$S = (\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH DI-*p*-TOLYLTHIOVIOLURIC ACID AT 30°

Cations	$\Delta G(K \text{ cal/mole})$			$\Delta H(K \text{ cal/mole})$			$\Delta S(\text{cals/mole})$		
	ΔG_1°	ΔG_2°	$\Delta G^\circ(\beta_3)$	ΔH_1°	ΔH_2°	$\Delta H^\circ(\beta_3)$	ΔS_1°	ΔS_2°	$\Delta S^\circ(\beta_3)$
H ⁺									
Mn ²⁺	-4.01	-3.12	-7.13	-	-	-16.38	-	-	-30.3
Cd ²⁺	-4.26	-3.87	-8.13	-	-	-12.996	-	-30.09	-29.7
Zn ²⁺	-6.34	-5.08	-11.42	-16.75	-3.078	-18.69	-34.30	-6.30	-23.9
Pb ²⁺	-5.23	-6.43	-11.66	-13.1	-9.70	-22.8	-25.90	-10.8	-36.7
Co ²⁺	-6.32	-5.69	-12.01	-11.4	-11.400	-21.88	-16.7	-18.8	-32.5
Ni ²⁺	-7.07	-5.69	-12.76	-12.39	-6.042	-19.70	-17.50	-1.10	-22.9
Fe ²⁺	-6.63	-5.49	-12.12	-9.46	-12.880	-21.66	-9.30	-22.1	-31.4
Cu ²⁺	-7.10	-6.97	-13.07	-11.400	-7.132	-20.52	-14.10	-4.0	-24.5
UO ₂ ²⁺	-7.02	-6.07	-13.21	-8.560	-11.300	-19.91	-5.05	-17.05	-22.1

To evaluate the overall enthalpy change $\log K$ was plotted against $1/T$; wherever a straight line was not obtained, a tangent was drawn at the respective temperature, and slope obtained was equated to $-\Delta H^\circ/4.57$.

The overall free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes at 30° are being reported in Table 3. It is seen that ΔG° values are negative, showing that complex formation is spontaneous. However, the values for enthalpy and entropy both are negative indicating that, the complex formation reactions occur with the liberation of energy and that the entropy term is not favourable for complex formation.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (DPG) is thankful to University Grants Commission, N. Delhi for financial assistance.

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